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Evaluation of Student Services Programs of Northwest Samar State University, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The country's effort of improving the student services programs is paralleled by the International Association of Student Affairs and Services (IASAS), an informal confederation of higher education student affairs/services professionals from around the world. Its members have been actively engaged for improving communication and sharing of professional development experiences such as best practices, internships, exchanges, conferences, colloquia and symposia. The status of implementation of student services programs of Northwest Samar State University (NwSSU) on terms of student welfare, student development, and institutional student services programs was very satisfactory. There is no significant difference in the status of implementation of student services programs of NwSSU in terms of student welfare, student development, and institutional student services programs with the different program components such as objectives, personnel, projects/activities, budget, facilities/equipment and monitoring and evaluation. The primary problems in the implementation of student services programs of NwSSU includes lack of qualified personnel, lack of facilities and equipment and lack of cooperation among partner agencies. Recommendations such as seminars / sessions on Personality Development Program and Proper Handling of Student Services Clients be conducted by the SAS Personnel; increase the number of personnel in the Registrar's Office, Guidance Office and Medical – Dental Clinic; hire licensed, educationally qualified librarians and guidance counselors; increase the budget allocation for the purchase of medicines; have a separate room for testing and group counseling purposes; procure additional copies of test materials; update the facilities and equipment in every SAS Unit, especially, the units with fiduciary fund.

INTRODUCTION

Higher Education Institutions must provide a set of student-centered activities and services in support of academic instruction intended to facilitate holistic and well-rounded student development for active involvement as future responsible citizens and leaders is embedded in RA No. 7722 otherwise known as the "Higher Education Act of 1994". The country's effort of improving the student services programs is paralleled by the International Association of Student Affairs and Services (IASAS), an informal confederation of higher education student affairs/services professionals from around the world. Its members have been actively engaged for improving communication and sharing of professional development experiences such as best practices, internships, exchanges, conferences, colloquia and symposia (UNESCO, 2002). IASAS developed a manual which includes basic assumptions of meeting student needs through an effective student affairs and services programmes, different models of professional preparation, effective management in student affairs and services and resources to be utilized in the implementation of student services programs (UNESCO, 2002).

Similarly, Accrediting Agency of Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACUP) devise an instrument on how to evaluate the student services programs of every academic institutions in the country. Area IV is Support to Students with parameters on Student Services Program (SSP), Student Welfare, Student Development,

Institutional Student Programs and Services, and Research, Monitoring and Evaluation. The level of accreditation will speak how a school considered the parameters against the standards set by the AACUP.

Speaking of evaluation, CMO No. 47 series of 2008 stipulated the Search for the Best Student Services Program Award. This recognizes and awards institutions whose outstanding student services programs were developed and implemented in support of the students' academic success and development as envisioned by the provisions of CMO No. 21 series of 2006. It aimed to provide impetus for enhancing student services in public and private Higher Education Institutions, promote greater appreciation on the importance of rendering effective and efficient student services and to recognize excellence in student services in HEIs (CHED, 2008).

Based on the foregoing discussions, the researcher is prompted to conceptualize a study to determine the status of student services programs of Northwest Samar State University, Calbayog City. This study hopes to provide an objective evaluation on the program objectives, projects/activities, personnel, budget, facilities and equipment, and monitoring and evaluation of each of the student services programs.

Research Problems

The study aims to determine the status of implementation of student services in Northwest Samar State University, Calbayog City with the end view of proposing program improvements.

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Specifically, it seeks answer to the following questions:

1. What is the status of implementation of student services programs of Northwest Samar State University, Calbayog City as perceived by the school administrators, SAS personnel, faculty, and students as to:

- 1.1 objectives;
- 1.2 projects/activities;
- 1.3 personnel;
- 1.4 budget;
- 1.5 facilities and equipment; and
- 1.6 monitoring and evaluation?

2. Are there significant differences in the perception of the four groups of respondents on the status of implementation of student services programs of Northwest Samar State University, Calbayog City in terms of the aforementioned program components?

3. What are the problems encountered in the implementation of student services programs of Northwest Samar State University, Calbayog City?

4. Based on the findings of the study, what program improvements can be proposed?

LITERATURE REVIEW

CMO No. 9, series of 2013 otherwise known as “Enhanced Policies and Guidelines on Student Affairs and Services” is the mantra followed by State Colleges and Universities (SUCs). This aims to set minimum standards on student affairs and services among Higher Education Institution (HEIs) in order to ensure proper balance between rights of educational institution and student rights, improve the quality of SAS, promote access to quality, relevant, efficient and effective student affairs and services, support student development and welfare and ensure that all HEIs provide holistic approach for SAS and comply with the minimum requirements (CHED, 2013).

From the abovementioned CMO, it emphasized that each academic institution must consider student welfare. These are basic services that are necessary to serve the well-being of students. These include information, orientation and awareness, guidance and counseling, career and placement, economic enterprise development, and student handbook development. Information and orientation services refer to informative activities and materials designed to facilitate student adjustment to life in tertiary/higher education. On the other hand, guidance services are sets of services using an integrated approach to the development of well-functioning individuals primarily by helping them to utilize their potentials to the fullest. Career and job placement services refer to the assistance provided for vocational and occupational fitness and employment. Economic enterprise development refers to those services and programs that would cater to the other economic needs of students such as but not limited to student cooperatives, entrepreneurial, income generating projects and savings (CHED, 2013).

Along with the student welfare, said CMO also highlighted the student development. These are programs and activities designed for the enhancement and deepening

of leadership skills and social responsibility which include student organization and activities, professional organization or societies, special interests, leadership training programs, student council/government, student discipline and student publication/media.

Student organizations and activities refer to the recognition/accreditation, supervision and monitoring of student groups including the evaluation of their activities. While leadership training are programs and opportunities to develop and enhance leadership effectiveness in the personal level and student organizations. Student council/government refers to the student body duly organized and elected at large by the student themselves with due recognition and authority from the HEI as the students’ official representative in matters affecting them. There is also student discipline which refers to the judicious implementation of institutional rules and regulations governing student behavior and conduct and student publication refers to the official publication and such other student oriented print and non-print media of the university (CHED, 2013).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study used descriptive design in describing the variables with the aid of AACUP instrument Area IV on Support to Students. Descriptive design is devoted to the gathering of information about prevailing conditions or situations for the purpose of description and interpretation. A questionnaire was used in the conduct of the study where Part I described the profile of NwSSU; Part II described the perception of the four groups of respondents on the status of implementation of student services programs; and Part III was on the problems encountered in the implementation of student services programs.

The study utilized universal sampling for the administrators and Student Affairs Services personnel. On the other hand, purposive sampling for faculty and students was used to determine the respondents of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following tables present the results of the study:

Status of Implementation of SAS in NwSSU

Tables 1 to 21 described the status of implementation of student services programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of student welfare, student development and institutional student programs and services. Information and Orientation Services. Table 1 presents the status of implementation of student services programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of student welfare – information and orientation services. The data shows administrators, program implementers, faculty and students in Northwest Samar State University found out that the information and orientation services is very satisfactory. This implies that components of program as to information and orientation services is well-taken by the concerned office.

Table 1. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Student Welfare – Information and Orientation Services

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.80	0.69	7	4.11	0.64	20	4.08	0.60	116	4.06	0.60
Project/Activities	4	3.60	0.37	7	3.83	0.37	20	3.79	0.33	116	3.77	0.34
Personnel	4	3.55	0.41	7	3.89	0.41	20	3.77	0.31	116	3.77	0.34
Budget	4	3.35	0.19	7	3.46	0.30	20	3.40	0.28	116	3.41	0.27
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.30	0.35	7	3.57	0.42	20	3.46	0.33	116	3.47	0.35
M & E	4	3.50	0.12	7	3.66	0.41	20	3.56	0.30	116	3.58	0.30

Guidance and Counseling Services.

Table 2 presents the status of implementation of student services programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of student welfare – guidance and counseling services. The data shows administrators, program

implementers, faculty and students in Northwest Samar State University found out that the guidance and counseling services is very satisfactory. This implies that components of program as to guidance and counseling is well-taken by the concerned office and able to dispense

Table 2. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Students Welfare – Guidance and Counseling Services

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.25	0.10	7	3.37	0.55	20	3.26	0.50	116	3.28	0.46
Project/Activities	4	3.50	0.35	7	3.54	0.47	20	3.52	0.43	116	3.52	0.41
Personnel	4	3.45	0.41	7	3.66	0.41	20	3.61	0.43	116	3.60	0.41
Budget	4	3.40	0.37	7	3.57	0.45	20	3.53	0.38	116	3.53	0.38
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.35	0.10	7	3.37	0.24	20	3.39	0.31	116	3.38	0.27
M & E	4	3.05	0.10	7	3.20	0.45	20	3.15	0.37	116	3.15	0.35

the different services to the clientele effectively.

NwSSU administrators, program implementers, faculty and students described the career and job placement services as very satisfactory. This implies that, there are clear programs and activities organized in order to address the needs of clientele as to career orientation and

Career and Job Placement Services.

Table 3 presents the status of implementation of student services programs in NwSSU in terms of student welfare –career and job placement services. Based on the data,

Table 3. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Student Welfare – Career and Job Placement Services

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	3	3.80	0.69	7	3.86	0.59	20	3.78	0.59	116	3.82	0.56
Project/Activities	3	4.13	0.99	7	4.20	0.84	20	4.09	0.83	116	4.14	0.80
Personnel	3	3.53	0.50	7	3.63	0.27	20	3.51	0.36	116	3.57	0.37
Budget	3	3.53	0.31	7	3.49	0.23	20	3.42	0.32	116	3.45	0.29
Facilities/Equipment	3	3.40	0.35	7	3.37	0.18	20	3.39	0.18	116	3.38	0.19
M & E	3	3.87	0.12	7	3.86	0.28	20	3.84	0.15	116	3.84	0.18

proper job placement in the University.

Student Handbook Development.

Economic Enterprise Development.

Table 4 presents the status of implementation of student services programs in NwSSU in terms of student welfare – economic enterprise development. The data shows that NwSSU administrators, program implementers, faculty and students found that economic enterprise development is very satisfactory as reflected in their means and SD. This implies that the respondents appreciated the different program components of economic enterprise development.

Table 5 presents the status of implementation of student services programs in NwSSU in terms of student welfare – student handbook development. The data shows that NwSSU administrators, program implementers, faculty and students found out that student handbook development is very satisfactory as shown in their mean and SD. This implies that respondents appreciated the significant of having student handbook as this embody the policies of the university.

Table 4. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Student Welfare – Economic Enterprise Development

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	3	3.73	0.23	7	3.57	0.18	20	3.61	0.17	116	3.62	0.17
Project/Activities	3	3.47	0.42	7	3.34	0.19	20	3.42	0.34	116	3.39	0.31
Personnel	3	3.53	0.12	7	3.66	0.22	20	3.57	0.23	116	3.59	0.21
Budget	3	3.53	0.23	7	3.49	0.16	20	3.49	0.14	116	3.49	0.14
Facilities/Equipment	3	3.60	0.60	7	3.77	0.31	20	3.74	0.31	116	3.74	0.33
M & E	3	3.73	0.70	7	3.74	0.22	20	3.68	0.21	116	3.71	0.27

Table 5. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Students Welfare – Student Handbook Development

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.55	0.25	7	3.60	0.31	20	3.53	0.25	116	3.55	0.25
Project/Activities	4	3.65	0.10	7	3.63	0.18	20	3.53	0.16	116	3.57	0.16
Personnel	4	3.45	0.19	7	3.43	0.21	20	3.41	0.14	116	3.42	0.16
Budget	4	3.70	0.20	7	3.66	0.15	20	3.58	0.28	116	3.62	0.24
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.60	0.43	7	3.69	0.25	20	3.62	0.30	116	3.64	0.29
M & E	4	3.60	0.28	7	3.51	0.36	20	3.50	0.26	116	3.52	0.28

Student Body Organization.

Table 6 presents the status of implementation of student services programs in NwSSU in terms of student development – student body organization. The data shows that NwSSU administrators, program implementers,

faculty and students described the student body organization as very satisfactory as reflected in its means and SD. Such observation is valid since student body organizations are supported by the NwSSU academic community as evidenced on several projects and activities

Table 6. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Students Development – Student Body Organization

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.65	0.19	7	3.69	0.16	20	3.68	0.16	116	3.68	0.16
Project/Activities	4	3.70	0.20	7	3.57	0.24	20	3.61	0.33	116	3.61	0.28
Personnel	4	3.65	0.30	7	3.66	0.32	20	3.65	0.24	116	3.65	0.26
Budget	4	3.60	0.16	7	3.63	0.31	20	3.56	0.23	116	3.58	0.24
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.65	0.10	7	3.71	0.20	20	3.67	0.31	116	3.68	0.26
M & E	4	4.05	0.19	7	4.06	0.15	20	4.11	0.20	116	4.09	0.18

towards the leadership development of students.

student services programs in NwSSU in terms of student development-student discipline. The data shows that NwSSU administrators, program-implementers,

Student Discipline

Table 7 presents the status of implementation of

Table 7. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Students Development – Student Discipline

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.80	0.43	7	3.80	0.37	20	3.79	0.35	116	3.79	0.35
Project/Activities	4	3.75	0.50	7	3.71	0.49	20	3.65	0.49	116	3.68	0.47
Personnel	4	3.60	0.33	7	3.60	0.31	20	3.58	0.27	116	3.59	0.28
Budget	4	3.60	0.28	7	3.74	0.19	20	3.61	0.22	116	3.64	0.22
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.65	0.19	7	3.69	0.20	20	3.58	0.16	116	3.62	0.17
M & E	4	3.35	0.19	7	3.29	0.43	20	3.31	0.25	116	3.31	0.28

faculty and students described the students discipline as very satisfactory with the means and SD reflected. This implies that student discipline was given priority in the formulation of policies and its implementation was carried out effectively. Furthermore, students are responsive accordingly which explains that they are being informed on whatever guidelines about discipline and heard before the imposition of sanctions.

Student Publication/Yearbook.

Table 8 presents the status of implementation of student services programs in NwSSU in terms of student

development - student publication/yearbook. The data shows that NwSSU administrators, program-implementers, faculty and students rated student development – student publication/yearbook as very satisfactory as suggested by the means and SD. This implies that student publication is manned by qualified and responsible persons who was able to dispense the functions of the office. Relevant outputs as to the release of school paper and entries on it are being followed up. In addition, publication staff are motivated to carry out their job and mentor fellow and younger breed of writers and contributors.

Table 8. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Students Development – Student Publication/Yearbook

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.50	0.35	7	3.43	0.27	20	3.54	0.36	116	3.51	0.33
Project/Activities	4	3.75	0.10	7	3.80	0.12	20	3.79	0.12	116	3.79	0.11
Personnel	4	3.85	0.34	7	3.77	0.21	20	3.78	0.14	116	3.79	0.19
Budget	4	3.80	0.16	7	3.60	0.26	20	3.67	0.25	116	3.67	0.24
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.40	0.28	7	3.51	0.28	20	3.43	0.35	116	3.45	0.31
M & E	4	3.85	0.30	7	3.83	0.27	20	3.76	0.20	116	3.79	0.22

Admission Services.

Table 9 presents the status of implementation of student services programs in NwSSU in terms of institutional student programs and services – admission services. The data shows that NwSSU administrators, program-

implementers, faculty and students rated admission services as very satisfactory given the means and SD in the table. This implies that respondents appreciated the manner of selection/screening of new entrants who applied for any program in the university. Moreover,

Table 9. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services – Admission Services

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	4.60	0.80	7	4.51	0.76	20	4.39	0.85	116	4.45	0.79
Project/Activities	4	3.55	0.34	7	3.74	0.34	20	3.62	0.27	116	3.64	0.29
Personnel	4	3.80	0.33	7	3.80	0.23	20	3.73	0.33	116	3.76	0.29
Budget	4	3.75	0.25	7	3.60	0.23	20	3.63	0.31	116	3.64	0.28
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.75	0.10	7	3.74	0.10	20	3.73	0.10	116	3.74	0.09
M & E	4	3.85	0.53	7	3.89	0.49	20	3.63	0.27	116	3.72	0.37

this could be attributed to the wide dissemination of information to the service area and the promotion of programs made by the different colleges.

Scholarship and Financial Assistance

Table 10 presents the status of implementation of

student services programs in NwSSU in terms of institutional student programs and services – scholarship and financial assistance. The data shows that NwSSU administrators, program-implementers, faculty and students rated the scholarship and financial assistance as

Table 10. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services – Scholarship and Financial Assistance

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	4.60	0.80	7	4.51	0.76	20	4.39	0.85	116	4.45	0.79
Project/Activities	4	3.55	0.34	7	3.74	0.34	20	3.62	0.27	116	3.64	0.29
Personnel	4	3.80	0.33	7	3.80	0.23	20	3.73	0.33	116	3.76	0.29
Budget	4	3.75	0.25	7	3.60	0.23	20	3.63	0.31	116	3.64	0.28
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.75	0.10	7	3.74	0.10	20	3.73	0.10	116	3.74	0.09
M & E	4	3.85	0.53	7	3.89	0.49	20	3.63	0.27	116	3.72	0.37

very satisfactory with the means and SD in the table. This implies that respondents were aware of the functionality of the scholarship and financial assistance provided to the students and they appreciated the impact of said student support extended. In addition, the selection and determination of recipients was justified as the procedure was wide disseminated to all students. Thus, there was

Table 11. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services – Food Services

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.90	0.26	7	3.74	0.38	20	3.77	0.30	116	3.78	0.30
Project/Activities	4	3.80	0.23	7	3.71	0.38	20	3.68	0.28	116	3.71	0.28
Personnel	4	3.60	0.16	7	3.97	0.29	20	3.66	0.34	116	3.73	0.33
Budget	4	3.90	0.50	7	3.60	0.23	20	3.63	0.36	116	3.67	0.34
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.75	0.19	7	3.60	0.23	20	3.60	0.23	116	3.63	0.22
M & E	4	3.50	0.20	7	3.49	0.11	20	3.52	0.15	116	3.51	0.14

-implementers, faculty and students rated the food services as very satisfactory with the means and SD in the table. This implies that respondents are satisfied with the management who select the stall concessioners and approve the service contract and eventually recommend the kind of food availed, the price of the food and its safety.

Health Services

Table 12 presents the status of implementation of student

Table 12. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services – Health Services

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.70	0.26	7	3.66	0.46	20	3.64	0.41	116	3.65	0.39
Project/Activities	4	3.70	0.48	7	3.60	0.28	20	3.65	0.26	116	3.65	0.29
Personnel	4	3.65	0.10	7	3.60	0.31	20	3.57	0.27	116	3.59	0.26
Budget	4	3.65	0.19	7	3.60	0.16	20	3.57	0.33	116	3.59	0.28
Facilities/Equipment	4	4.05	0.47	7	4.03	0.21	20	3.98	0.47	116	4.00	0.41
M & E	4	3.95	0.10	7	3.83	0.39	20	3.72	0.39	116	3.78	0.36

Safety and Security Services.

Table 13 presents the status of implementation of student services programs in NwSSU in terms of student programs and services – safety and security services. The data shows that NwSSU administrators, program-implementers, faculty and students rated the safety and

equitable distribution of scholarship and financial assistance among clientele in the university.

Food Services

Table 11 presents the status of implementation of student services programs in NwSSU in terms of institutional student programs and services – food services. The data shows that NwSSU administrators, program

services programs of NwSSU in terms of institutional student programs and services – health services. The data shows that NwSSU administrators, program-implementers, faculty and students rated the health services as very satisfactory with the means and SD in the table. This implies that respondents are satisfied with the services availed from the medical and dental services throughout the school year.

Table 13. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services – Safety and Security Services

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.80	0.54	7	3.69	0.34	20	3.76	0.40	116	3.75	0.38
Project/Activities	4	3.90	0.35	7	3.77	0.39	20	3.73	0.35	116	3.76	0.34
Personnel	4	3.75	0.19	7	3.83	0.41	20	3.73	0.34	116	3.77	0.33
Budget	4	3.70	0.20	7	3.69	0.25	20	3.64	0.26	116	3.66	0.24
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.55	0.25	7	3.46	0.22	20	3.54	0.31	116	3.52	0.26
M & E	4	3.80	0.16	7	3.60	0.23	20	3.60	0.37	116	3.64	0.32

security services as very satisfactory with the means and SD in the table. This implies that respondents were satisfied in the delivery of services on this aspect. They felt safe and secure while they are inside the university. This could be attributed to the selection of security personnel who take their posts courteously and efficiently

day and night in the school premises.

Student Housing and Residential Services

Table 14 presents the status of implementation of student programs and services in NwSSU in terms of institutional student programs and services-student housing and residential services. The data shows that

NwSSU administrators, program- implementers, faculty and students rated student housing and residential services as very satisfactory with the mean and SD in the table. This implies that respondents were satisfied with the services and there are no complaints and grudges heard posed by any clientele on this aspect of services.

Table 14. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services – Student Housing and Residential Services

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.60	0.16	7	3.63	0.14	20	3.63	0.15	116	3.62	0.14
Project/Activities	4	3.80	0.23	7	3.77	0.35	20	3.69	0.41	116	3.72	0.37
Personnel	4	3.55	0.34	7	3.63	0.18	20	3.57	0.25	116	3.58	0.24
Budget	4	3.65	0.25	7	3.60	0.23	20	3.53	0.28	116	3.57	0.26
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.55	0.19	7	3.54	0.22	20	3.59	0.22	116	3.58	0.21
M & E	4	4.60	0.80	7	4.54	0.78	20	4.44	0.78	116	4.49	0.75

Multi-Faith Services

Table 15 presents the status of implementation of student services programs of NwSSU in terms of institutional student programs and services – multi-faith services. The data shows that NwSSU administrators, program-implementers, faculty and students rated the multi-faith

services as very satisfactory with the means and SD in the table. This implies that respondents recognized that there is the respect of faith and religion observed in the university as shown in the classroom settings, student organizations, and conduct of different programs and activities.

Table 15. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services – Multi-Faith Services

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.80	0.43	7	3.80	0.53	20	3.73	0.46	116	3.76	0.46
Project/Activities	4	3.75	0.25	7	3.74	0.25	20	3.71	0.14	116	3.72	0.18
Personnel	4	3.85	0.30	7	3.60	0.28	20	3.57	0.41	116	3.62	0.37
Budget	4	3.95	0.38	7	3.94	0.32	20	3.87	0.25	116	3.91	0.28
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.95	0.10	7	3.80	0.20	20	3.78	0.35	116	3.82	0.29
M & E	4	3.75	0.19	7	3.74	0.40	20	3.68	0.33	116	3.71	0.32

Foreign/International Student Services

Table 16 presents the status of implementation of student programs and services of NwSSU in terms of institutions student program and services – foreign/international student services. The data shows that

NwSSU administrators, program-implementers, faculty and students rated the foreign/international student services as very satisfactory with means and SD in the table. This implies that respondents were satisfied in delivery of the service.

Table 16. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services – Foreign/International Student Services

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.75	0.19	7	3.63	0.37	20	3.74	0.42	116	3.71	0.37
Project/Activities	4	4.05	0.41	7	3.80	0.37	20	3.71	0.35	116	3.79	0.36
Personnel	4	3.70	0.26	7	3.69	0.38	20	3.76	0.38	116	3.74	0.36
Budget	4	3.70	0.48	7	3.71	0.32	20	3.68	0.21	116	3.69	0.27
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.90	0.26	7	3.89	0.45	20	3.71	0.30	116	3.78	0.33
M & E	4	3.80	0.28	7	3.60	0.26	20	3.59	0.25	116	3.63	0.25

Services for Students with Special Needs and Persons with Disabilities

Table 17 presents the status of implementation of student services programs of NwSSU in terms of

institutional student services programs – services for students with special needs and persons with disabilities. The data shows that the NwSSU administrators, program – implementers, faculty and students rated services for

Table 17. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services – Services for Students with Special Needs and Persons with Disabilities

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.90	0.48	7	3.71	0.38	20	3.69	0.30	116	3.74	0.34
Project/Activities	4	3.65	0.25	7	3.71	0.32	20	3.59	0.29	116	3.64	0.29
Personnel	4	3.75	0.25	7	3.66	0.28	20	3.53	0.24	116	3.60	0.25
Budget	4	3.65	0.10	7	3.77	0.21	20	3.69	0.29	116	3.71	0.25
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.65	0.34	7	3.66	0.22	20	3.52	0.26	116	3.58	0.26
M & E	4	3.95	0.19	7	3.89	0.40	20	3.71	0.35	116	3.80	0.34

students with special needs and persons with disabilities as very satisfactory with the means and SD in the table. This implies that respondents observed that this sector is given attention and priority in the delivery of any service in the university.

Cultural and Arts Program.

Table 18 presents the status of implementation of student services programs of NwSSU in terms of institutional student programs and services -cultural and arts program. The data shows that NwSSU administrators, program-

Table 18. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services – Cultural and Arts Program

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.65	0.30	7	3.71	0.28	20	3.64	0.24	116	3.67	0.25
Project/Activities	4	3.70	0.12	7	3.86	0.41	20	3.66	0.40	116	3.73	0.37
Personnel	4	3.70	0.26	7	3.63	0.24	20	3.53	0.28	116	3.58	0.27
Budget	4	3.85	0.19	7	3.86	0.32	20	3.71	0.26	116	3.78	0.26
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.90	0.35	7	3.86	0.40	20	3.84	0.50	116	3.85	0.44
M & E	4	3.80	0.43	7	3.74	0.53	20	3.70	0.44	116	3.72	0.44

implementers, faculty and students rated cultural and arts program as very satisfactory with the means and SD in the table. This implies that respondents were able to observe and eventually satisfied with participation of university in any cultural and arts activities local, national and even international.

Sports and Development Programs

Table 19 presents the status of implementation of student programs and services of NwSSU in terms of institutional

student programs and services – sports and development programs. The data shows that NwSSU administrators, program-implementers, faculty and students rated sports and development programs as very satisfactory with the means and SD in the table. This implies that respondents were satisfied in the management of this service. Furthermore, respondents were part in any sports and activities designed for the development program of the academic community.

Table 19. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services – Sports and Development Programs

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.80	0.43	7	3.77	0.44	20	3.78	0.39	116	3.78	0.39
Project/Activities	4	3.85	0.47	7	3.69	0.28	20	3.67	0.41	116	3.72	0.38
Personnel	4	3.60	0.49	7	3.74	0.47	20	3.71	0.39	116	3.71	0.41
Budget	4	3.55	0.34	7	3.71	0.25	20	3.51	0.30	116	3.58	0.30
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.55	0.19	7	3.29	0.20	20	3.26	0.28	116	3.31	0.26
M & E	4	3.45	0.10	7	3.46	0.15	20	3.42	0.14	116	3.43	0.14

Social and Community Involvement Program

Table 20 presents the status of implementation of student services programs of NwSSU in terms of institutional student services programs – social and community involvement program. The data shows the NwSSU administrators, program -implementers, faculty and students rated social and community involvement

program as very satisfactory with the means and SD in the table. This implies that respondents observed the active participation of NwSSU in the community. Other Related Programs and Services. Table 21 presents the status of implementation of student services programs of NwSSU in terms of institutional student programs and services – other related programs and services.

Table 20. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services – Social and Community Involvement Program

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.60	0.16	7	3.63	0.18	20	3.63	0.20	116	3.63	0.18
Project/Activities	4	3.70	0.20	7	3.74	0.28	20	3.60	0.28	116	3.65	0.27
Personnel	4	3.50	0.26	7	3.57	0.34	20	3.42	0.28	116	3.48	0.29
Budget	4	3.70	0.35	7	3.57	0.21	20	3.53	0.31	116	3.57	0.29
Facilities/Equipment	4	4.40	0.80	7	4.34	0.78	20	4.24	0.78	116	4.29	0.75
M & E	4	3.90	0.35	7	3.83	0.34	20	3.73	0.35	116	3.78	0.34

Table 21. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services – Other Related Programs and Services

Components	Administrator			Implementer			Faculty			Students		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
Objectives	4	3.80	0.28	7	3.86	0.40	20	3.79	0.35	116	3.81	0.33
Project/Activities	4	3.40	0.16	7	3.37	0.18	20	3.45	0.24	116	3.42	0.21
Personnel	4	3.60	0.28	7	3.69	0.16	20	3.76	0.24	116	3.72	0.23
Budget	4	3.80	0.16	7	3.91	0.34	20	3.94	0.33	116	3.91	0.31
Facilities/Equipment	4	3.40	0.43	7	3.37	0.44	20	3.36	0.28	116	3.37	0.33
M & E	4	3.55	0.34	7	3.54	0.28	20	3.46	0.31	116	3.49	0.29

The data shows that NwSSU administrators, program-implementers, faculty and student rated the other related programs and services as very satisfactory with the means and SD in the table. This implies that the respondents were satisfied with the delivery of all other related programs and services.

Difference in the Perceptions of Respondents

Table 22 to 26 presents the test of significant different of student services programs of NwSSU in terms of student welfare, student development, and institutional student programs and services as described by the NwSSU administrators, program-implementers, faculty and students.

Student Welfare

Table 22 presents the test of significant difference of the program components and the student services programs of NwSSU in terms of student welfare particularly information and orientation services, guidance and counseling, career and job placement, economic enterprise development and student handbook/yearbook. The data shows that NwSSU student welfare as to information and orientation services, guidance and counseling, career and job placement, economic enterprise development, and student handbook/yearbook were described by the NwSSU administrators, program-implementer, faculty and students to be not significant as to programs

Table 22. Test of Significant Difference of the Program Components and the Student Services Programs of NwSSU in terms of Student Welfare

Components	Info & Orient.			Guidance & Counseling			Career & Job Placement			Economic Enterprise Devt			Student Handbook/Yearbook		
	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.
Objectives	3	0.272	0.845	3	0.106	0.957	3	0.039	0.990	3	0.628	0.598	3	0.136	0.938
Projects/Activities	3	0.433	0.730	3	0.012	0.998	3	0.038	0.990	3	0.184	0.907	3	1.028	0.382
Personnel	3	0.814	0.488	3	0.230	0.876	3	0.249	0.862	3	0.361	0.781	3	0.089	0.966
Budget	3	0.143	0.934	3	0.179	0.910	3	0.191	0.903	3	0.092	0.964	3	0.377	0.770
Facilities/Equipment	3	0.526	0.665	3	0.029	0.993	3	0.030	0.993	3	0.198	0.897	3	0.106	0.956
M & E	3	0.265	0.851	3	0.153	0.928	3	0.031	0.993	3	0.129	0.943	3	0.144	0.933

components namely objectives, projects/activities, personnel, budget, facilities/equipment and monitoring and evaluation.

Student Development

Table 23 presents test of significant difference of student

services programs of NwSSU in terms of student development particularly student body organization, student discipline, and student publication/yearbook as rated by the NwSSU administrators, program-implementers, faculty and students. The data shows that

Table 23. Test of Significant Difference of the Program Components and the Student Services Programs of NwSSU in terms of Student Development

Components	SBO			Student Discipline			Student Publication/Yearbook		
	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.
Objectives	3	0.047	0.987	3	0.002	1.000	3	0.198	0.898
Projects/Activities	3	0.176	0.912	3	0.069	0.977	3	0.177	0.912
Personnel	3	0.002	1.000	3	0.012	0.998	3	0.177	0.912
Budget	3	0.154	0.927	3	0.685	0.563	3	0.590	0.623
Facilities/Equipment	3	0.067	0.977	3	0.734	0.533	3	0.157	0.925
M & E	3	0.224	0.880	3	0.044	0.988	3	0.299	0.826

NwSSU student welfare as student body organization, student discipline, and student publication/yearbook were described by the NwSSU administrators, program-implementer, faculty and students to be not significant as to programs components namely objectives, projects/activities, personnel, budget, facilities/equipment and monitoring and evaluation. This implies that student development is well-taken and implemented in the university, thus respondents did not vary in appraising the different services classified under the student

development. They objectively described each component of the program services depending on the extent of the quality of service delivered to them as participants and collaborators.

Institutional Student Programs and Services

Table 24 presents the student service programs services in terms of institutional student programs and services particularly on admission, scholarship and financial assistance, food services, health services, and safety and security services. The data shows that NwSSU

Table 24. Test of Significant Difference of the Program Components and the Student Services Programs of NwSSU in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services

Components	Admission			Scholarship & Fin. Asst.			Food Services			Health Services			Safety & Security Services		
	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.
Objectives	3	0.100	0.960	3	0.091	0.965	3	0.261	0.853	3	0.027	0.994	3	0.091	0.965
Projects/Activities	3	0.461	0.710	3	0.116	0.951	3	0.202	0.895	3	0.105	0.957	3	0.271	0.846
Personnel	3	0.134	0.940	3	0.118	0.950	3	1.818	0.147	3	0.116	0.951	3	0.153	0.928
Budget	3	0.253	0.859	3	0.714	0.545	3	0.767	0.514	3	0.099	0.960	3	0.107	0.956
Facilities/Equipment	3	0.069	0.977	3	0.617	0.605	3	0.530	0.662	3	0.047	0.986	3	0.187	0.905
M & E	3	1.033	0.380	3	0.333	0.802	3	0.105	0.957	3	0.516	0.672	3	0.463	0.708

institutional student programs and services admission, scholarship and financial assistance, food services, health services, and safety and security services were described by the NwSSU administrators, program-implementer, faculty and students to be not significant as to programs components namely objectives, projects/activities, personnel, budget, facilities/equipment and monitoring and evaluation. This implies the service is well-taken and implemented in the university, thus respondents did not vary in appraising the different services classified under the student development.

Institutional Student Programs and Services

Table 25 presents the student service programs services in terms of institutional student programs and services particularly on student housing and residential services, multi-faith, foreign/international student, services for students with special needs and persons with disabilities and cultural and arts services. The data shows that NwSSU institutional student programs and services on sports and development program, social and communication

involvement program and other related were described by the NwSSU administrators, program-implementer, faculty and students to be not significant as to programs components namely objectives, projects/activities, personnel, budget, facilities/equipment and monitoring and evaluation.

Institutional Student Programs and Services

Table 26 presents the student service programs services in terms of institutional student programs and services particularly on sports and development program, social and community involvement program and others related program. The data shows that NwSSU institutional student programs and services on sports and development program, social and communication involvement program and other related were described by the NwSSU administrators, program-implementer, faculty and students to be not significant as to programs components namely objectives, projects/activities, personnel, budget, facilities/equipment and monitoring and evaluation.

Table 25. Test of Significant Difference of the Program Components and the Student Services Programs of NwSSU in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services

Components	Student Housing			Multi-Faith Services			Foreign/Inter. Stud. Services			Services for Std w/ Spec. Needs			Cultural and Arts Services		
	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.
Objectives	3	0.038	0.990	3	0.057	0.982	3	0.168	0.918	3	0.454	0.715	3	0.160	0.923
Projects/Activities	3	0.149	0.930	3	0.121	0.948	3	1.041	0.377	3	0.339	0.797	3	0.503	0.681
Personnel	3	0.125	0.945	3	0.658	0.579	3	0.090	0.966	3	1.134	0.338	3	0.587	0.625
Budget	3	0.319	0.811	3	0.181	0.909	3	0.032	0.992	3	0.248	0.862	3	0.748	0.525
Facilities/Equipment	3	0.125	0.945	3	0.393	0.758	3	0.719	0.542	3	0.627	0.598	3	0.021	0.996
M & E	3	0.069	0.977	3	0.104	0.958	3	0.808	0.492	3	0.874	0.456	3	0.063	0.979

Table 26. Test of Significant Difference of the Program Components and the Student Services Programs of NwSSU in terms of Student Development

Components	Sports & Development Program			Social & com Involvement Program			Others Related Prog.		
	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.	df	F	Sig.
Objectives	3	0.005	1.000	3	0.032	0.992	3	0.069	0.976
Projects/Activities	3	0.279	0.840	3	0.548	0.651	3	0.276	0.843
Personnel	3	0.112	0.953	3	0.535	0.659	3	0.637	0.592
Budget	3	0.833	0.478	3	0.403	0.751	3	0.232	0.874
Facilities/Equipment	3	1.385	0.250	3	0.069	0.977	3	0.017	0.997
M & E	3	0.156	0.926	3	0.367	0.777	3	0.200	0.896

Problems Encountered

Table 27 presents the problems encountered by the respondents in the implementation of student services programs of NwSSU. The data shows that the respondents were one in identifying that among the problems encountered in the implementation of student

services programs in NwSSU, lack of qualified personnel was considered as the primary problem. This could be attributed to the CHED guidelines. This was followed by lack of facilities and equipment and lack of cooperation among partner agencies.

Table 21. Status of Implementation of Student Services Programs in Northwest Samar State University in terms of Institutional Student Programs and Services – Other Related Programs and Services

Problems Encountered	Administrator		Implementer		Faculty		Students	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Lack of qualified personnel	4.25	0.50	4.29	0.49	4.35	0.49	4.32	0.47
Lack of facilities and equipment	3.50	1.00	3.43	0.98	3.30	0.98	3.36	0.94
Lack of information and campaign materials	3.25	0.50	3.29	0.49	3.35	0.49	3.32	0.47
Lack of updated evaluation instruments	2.75	0.50	2.71	0.49	2.65	0.49	2.68	0.47
Lack of office fixtures	3.50	1.00	3.43	0.98	3.30	0.98	3.36	0.94
Lack of trainings and professional growth opportunities	2.75	0.50	2.71	0.49	2.65	0.49	2.68	0.47
Lack promotion and information drive strategy	3.50	1.00	3.43	0.98	3.30	0.98	3.36	0.94
Less appeal of student services to students	2.75	0.50	2.71	0.49	2.65	0.49	2.68	0.47
Lack of enthusiasm in dealing the clients	3.50	1.00	3.43	0.98	3.30	0.98	3.36	0.94
Non-observance of the citizen's charter	3.75	0.50	3.71	0.49	3.65	0.49	3.68	0.47
No support on some national enabling laws	2.75	0.50	2.71	0.49	2.65	0.49	2.68	0.47
Non-compliance to CHED guidelines one way or another	3.75	0.50	3.71	0.49	3.65	0.49	3.68	0.47
Negative attitude towards conducting research relevant to student services	2.75	0.96	3.14	0.90	3.00	0.92	3.03	0.88
Lack of cooperation among partner agencies	3.50	0.58	3.29	0.49	3.55	0.51	3.47	0.50

CONCLUSION

Therefore, the study found out the following:

1.The status of implementation of student services programs of NwSSU on terms of student welfare, student development, and institutional student services programs was very satisfactory.

2.There is no significant difference in the status of implementation of student services programs of NwSSU in terms of student welfare, student development, and institutional student services programs with the different program components such as objectives, personnel, projects/activities, budget, facilities/equipment and monitoring and evaluation.

3.The primary problems in the implementation of student services programs of NwSSU includes lack of qualified personnel, lack of facilities and equipment and lack of cooperation among partner agencies.

RECOMMENDATION

1.Seminars / sessions on Personality Development Program and Proper Handling of Student Services Clients be conducted by the SAS Personnel

2.Increase the number of personnel in the Registrar's Office, Guidance Office and Medical – Dental Clinic

3.Hire licensed, educationally qualified librarians and guidance counselors

4.Increase the budget allocation for the purchase of medicines

5.Have a separate room for testing and group counseling purposes

6.Procure additional copies of test materials

7.Update the facilities and equipment in every SAS Unit , especially, the units with fiduciary fund

REFERENCES

CHED Memorandum Order No. 47, series 2008 known as Search for the Best Student Services Program Award

CHED Memorandum Order No. 9, series 2013 known as Enhanced Policies and Guidelines on Student Affairs and Services

Republic Act No. 7722 known as Higher Education Act of 1994

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2002). The Role of Student Affairs and Services in Higher Education, A Practical Manual for Developing, Implementing and Assessing Student Affairs Programmes and Services